

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Response of the leaffolder (LF) to extracts of resistant rice varieties

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We evaluated the response of LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée to extracts of resistant rices. Extracts of leaves were obtained by steam distillation followed by diethyl ether extraction. A 2,000 ppm solution of the oily extract was prepared by adding acetone. Ten 6-cm leaf pieces of susceptible TN1 were dipped in the solutions, dried, and infested with 5 4th-instar LF larvae per petri dish. The larvae had been starved for 3 h.

Extracts from TKM6, Darukasail, IR5865, and Kataribhog caused 39-46% larval mortality, compared with 9%

Toxicity of extracts of some resistant rices to LF eggs and larvae, ^a IRRI, 1985.

Variety	IRRI accession no.	Larval mortality ^b (%)	Unhatched eggs ^c (%)
TKM6	237	46 a	18 abc
Darukasail	45493	42 a	30 a
IR5865	39433	39 ab	11 abc
Kataribhog	46076	39 ab	14 abc
IR60	63493	37 abc	14 abc
BKN BR1008-21	—	31 abc	13 abc
IR50	53433	23 abc	20 abc
W1263	11657	18 bc	9 bc
ASD7	6303	13 bc	26 ab
IR36 (susceptible check)	30416	9 c	5 c

^aMeans followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

^bLarvae were fed TN1 leaves dipped in a 2,000 ppm solution of the extract. ^cEggs laid on TN1 leaves were dipped in a 2,000 ppm solution of the extract.

mortality for IR36 extract (see table). In another test, eggs laid on TN1 leaves were dipped in a 2,000 ppm extract of the distillate. Extracts from Darukasail

and ASD7 significantly reduced hatching, causing 30 and 26% unhatched eggs, compared with 5% for IR36 extract. *ℒ*

Laboratory evaluation of insecticides for controlling greenhorned caterpillar

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Greenhorned caterpillar *Melanitis leda ismene* (Cramer) attacked the second

Efficacy of insecticides for controlling greenhorned caterpillar larvae, Madurai, India.

Insecticide	Application rate (g ai/ha)	Larval mortality ^a (%)
Chlorpyrifos 20 EC	200	100 a
Fenvalerate 20 EC	50	100 a
FMC54800 100 EC	40	100 a
Endosulfan 35 EC	350	100 a
FMC65318 150 g/L	90	95 ab
FMC35001 25 EC	250	95 ab
Deltanet 400 EC	200	85 bc
Fenprothrin 10 EC	100	80 bc
Diflubenzuron 25 WP	75	25 d
Check	—	—

^aCalculated 24 h after insecticide treatment. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

season IR20 crop 1983-84 at ACRI. In a laboratory experiment, we evaluated four synthetic pyrethroids, two new insecticides, one chitin inhibitor, and two commonly used insecticides for caterpillar control. Potted IR20 plants were sprayed with insecticides and their leaves were fed to 4th-instar larvae. Treatments were in three replications of five larvae per treatment. Dead larvae

were counted 24 h after spraying and percent mortality was calculated (see table).

Fenvalerate, FMC54800, chlorpyrifos, and endosulfan were the most effective chemicals. Diflubenzuron caused only 25% mortality, and 75% of the surviving larvae became mosaics in larval or larval to pupal moltings. *ℒ*

Light trap catches cannot predict field population of green leafhopper (GLH)

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We studied the relationship between light trap catches and field populations of GLH at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore.

GLH on 20 randomly selected hills of Jaya were counted weekly from 30 to 60 d after transplanting in plots planted at monthly intervals from Jan 1982 to

Dec 1983. During the same period, light trap catches were recorded from a modified Robinson trap with a 125-W mercury vapor lamp. Mean daily catch over 7 d before the field count and the number of GLH/20 hills in the field were used in regression analysis to correlate field population with light trap catch. Ninety pairs of observations were analyzed.

The mean GLH trapped per night ranged from 0.01 to 138 and field population was 0 to 64. The regression of field population on light trap catch was not significant, and there was no correlation between light trap catches and field populations. *ℒ*